

Effects on earth at fast rotation

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In the book [1] we had calculated the pitch angle β . The planet's surface appears inclined with this angle to an observer. If the planet is not spherical, then there is a second angle, which takes the geometrical form of the planet into consideration. The sum of these two angles is the pitch angle γ . Now we assume that the angular velocity of the revolution solid (planet) is constant. Possible dependences of pitch angle γ from latitude α are drawn here.

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At sphere with constant density the case a) is valid. At all other revolution solids the cases a) or b) or c) are possible. We can sketch the slope of the horizon plane relative to the observer. $H(\alpha, \gamma)$ is the height, as appeared to the observer.

The figures correspond to the observer like a walk from north to south, from $\alpha = 90^\circ$ to $\alpha = 0^\circ$.

If there are masses on the revolution solid's surface that are only held by gravitation, these masses could be in motion at changed rotation time and especially at large angular velocity. These masses can "fall" or "slide" on the horizon plane $H(\alpha)$. The same is valid for fluids, on earth especially to

the water. The largest part of earth's surface is covered with water. The fluids would flow to latitudes α with $\gamma = 0$. But then southern from this place it must be $\gamma < 0$ in a neighbourhood. This is valid for the north part of the revolution solid. On the south part it is corresponding converse.

Now special to earth:

Depending from angular velocity and centrifugal force that changes the form of the earth (oblateness) the cases a) or b) or c) are possible. With that the water can flow to the equatorial belt and perhaps to other latitudes α . If the earth would be a sphere with constant density, the fluid only flows to the equatorial belt.

If it is at one latitude $\gamma > 90^\circ$ or $\gamma < -90^\circ$, a no bounded mass is repeled from the revolution solid (that means the mass flies into the space). The same is valid for fluids on earth especially for the water.

Now it shall be that $-90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 90^\circ$ at all latitudes α :

The water on earth collects as in case a), b) or c). If parts of oceans collect at the equator and perhaps at other latitudes, then in these latitudes large areas will be overflowed. At the equator for example it will be the middle of Africa, northern south America, the islands between Asia and Australia. The time and the "intensity" of this process depends from γ at singular latitudes.

Case I:

At small γ at all latitudes (for example $1^\circ < \gamma < 2^\circ$) the water flows only in rills to the "global collecting places". At some larger γ the water can flow in smaller or larger brooks (with different flow velocity). On the way to these global collecting places it arises in sinks depending from intensity small or large puddles or lakes, that can not dry up, scattered over all continents. Then the continents are "perforated" with puddles or lakes.

At global collecting places the water unites to larger rivers or in extreme cases to small seas that flow into the oceans. Simultaneous the water level rises at these areas. The reason is that water streams also from oceans and seas to global collecting places for example the equator. These can be considerable water masses. Because of this, deeper areas at global collecting places go under the water. This process can take in dependence of γ years or decades or still longer.

Case II:

If γ is larger, the brooks on continents changes to rivers that have in dependence of γ a very high flow velocity. These rivers don't need to be constant in their position, the rivers can shift in a few minutes or seconds some kilometres. At global collecting places small seas arise. There very large rivers flow into the oceans, In the oceans itself is also a stream to the global collecting places. With that the water level rises at global collecting places. Areas vanish in the water similar to Case I. But the process goes faster. In Case II an observer is only perhaps in the mountains quite positive.

Case III:

If γ is still larger, the seas can flow rather directly over the land to the global collecting areas that means the concerning land will be overflowed (perhaps with the exception of the high mountains) with high velocity. The effects to the areas at global collecting areas are the same as in Case I and Case II. But the times are still shorter. It is possible that the earth flies asunder. In Case II and III gas (for example air) condenses at global collecting places. With that there will be very strong storms. In these two cases other objects as for example houses, mountains, rocks, towers can be dragged along by the floods or by the strong inertia forces.

The flow of water masses can also be subterranean. Rivers and brooks can also have the following form:

Water masses can flow overground and underground. Perhaps the underground part can be much bigger. These rivers can also be very deep.

If it is $-90^\circ > \gamma$ or $\gamma > +90^\circ$ at determined latitudes, the water and other masses are flung to the outer space. If the initial velocity is smaller than the escape speed from the earth, the water and the other masses hit the earth and will be repelled again. This repeats so long as the escape speed from the earth is achieved. It is possible that the escape speed is never achieved. Orbits around the earth are possible. In the atmosphere the velocity is braked, till after a long time these masses fall perhaps to earth again.

If an observer is exactly at the pole (that means direct at earth's rotation axis), then there are no inertia forces nor at highest angular velocity. But near at pole is a centrifugal force and the visual vertical changes. The figure shows as an observer could see the pole:

If the angular velocity of the earth changes temporal, then there are further inertia forces. The same happens, if the position of earth's rotation axis is changed. Every inertia force changes the visual vertical.

Bibliography:

[1] Harald Schröder "Theory of orientation", Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002